

INTRODUCTORY SELECTION AND ASSESSMENT OF GRAIN
QUALITY OF BLACK GRAIN

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Abstract *Black bean is an annual herbaceous plant. The plant supplies itself with nitrogen through the bacteria in its roots. The stem is round and pointed. Its height is 30-130 cm, on average 50-60 cm, it branches well. Harvesting by mechanization is difficult due to the large area of the stem. Ripe pods are brown, almost black.*

Key words *growth temperature, legumes, mineral fertilizers, nitric acid rate, decomposition, liquid fertilizers.*

Black bean is superior to other leguminous crops, such as beans, chickpeas, and green peas, due to its content of protein and vitamins, its nutritional value, and its quick cooking time. Black bean:

protein - 24-28 percent, lysine - 8 percent, arginine - 7 percent, vitamin V1, RR, etc. [1].

Black bean is grown as a main and repeated crop in all regions of the republic. This crop is the best predecessor for all crops in the rotation system. If the seeds of soybeans, chickpeas, buckwheat, and lentils are not treated with inoculants before sowing, biological nitrogen will not be formed in their roots. Due to the fact that

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mosh is already planted in all the soils of the republic, biological nitrogen-fixing nodule bacteria naturally form in the soil and, depending on the thickness of the seedling, it accumulates an average of 80-120 kg of nitrogen per hectare. [2].

When planting mosh as a repeated crop in the field, the first crop is harvested quickly, when the soil is ripe, it is plowed to a depth of 20-22 cm, harrowed, and then crushed. If large lumps are formed on the ground, it is worked with heavy harrows or ring rollers. If the rows are to be worked, the soil is softened by cultivation at a depth of 10-12 cm without plowing, then it is plowed and the land is prepared for planting. [3].

30-40 kg of nitrogen, 40-60 kg of phosphorus, and 30-50 kg of potassium are applied per hectare when mosh is planted as a repeat crop requiring phosphorus and potassium fertilizers. Nitrogen is introduced by cultivation before planting. If 10-15 tons of rotted manure from organic fertilizers are applied per hectare, the seed yield will increase significantly.

For sowing, high-class seeds with a purity of 98.5% and a germination rate of not less than 92% are selected. Planting is carried out in the summer. In the southern regions of Uzbekistan, the period from June 15 to July 10 is the most optimal period for planting mash as a repeated crop. If sown too late, the crop may be damaged by frost or the grains may not ripen. Decomposition of high-carbonate phosphate rock at a nitric acid rate of 50-60% of stoichiometry in the presence of ammonium nitrate allows obtaining a complex nitrogen-phosphorus fertilizer with a high degree of assimilable components - nitrogen, phosphorus and calcium. But the decomposition products before drying are liquid, and the introduction of ammonium nitrate increases the hygroscopicity of the complex fertilizer. The conducted large-scale technological studies showed the fundamental possibility of obtaining liquid complex fertilizers (LCF) from the specified samples.

Black beans seeds are sown in rows at 45-50 cm, 60 cm or in double rows with 60 cm between rows. In this case, the distance between the double rows is 13-15 cm. In weed-free, well-cultivated fields, mosh can be planted in rows (15 cm).

Care of replanted mosh consists of inter-row cultivation, weeding and watering during the growing season.

Black bean is irrigated 1-2 times during the growth period, flowering and pod formation at the rate of 800-1000 cubic meters per hectare. When mosh is planted as a siderate crop, with the formation of pods, it is pressed transversely with a mola, disked and plowed to a depth of 27-30 cm. Mung beans do not ripen evenly. Ripe pods turn black, and the grains acquire a characteristic color. Harvesting begins when 70 percent of the pods are ripe. Mowing is carried out with a hay mower, or JBA35 and other machines, and it is harvested immediately.

Plants are harvested after drying for 3-4 days. When sown for hay, the green mass is harvested when the plants are in full bloom. Crushed, cleaned seeds are stored in bags or spilled in ventilated buildings with a moisture content of no more than 15 percent. When planted in July, the yield is relatively 3-4 s/ha.unit for receiving, storing and feeding phosphate raw materials;

In 2005, it was recommended to plant in the territory of the republic. The variety was created by individual selection. Ripening period 90–95 days, yield 14–16 s/ha, plant height 95–100 cm, seed protein content 22–24%, weight of 1000 seeds 60–65 g, stem black It has a stem-like appearance, yellow flowers, an early variety, the sowing period is up to June 20 in a repeated crop, the rate of seed sowing is 10–12 kg.

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